

Co-Creating Circular
Resource Flows in Cities

constRuctive mEtabolic processes For materiaL fLOWs in
urban and peri-urban environments across Europe

Deliverable 2.2

REFLOW OS

Due date of deliverable: 30/11/2019
Actual submission date: 1/12/2019
Start date of project: 01/06/2019 Duration (36 Months)
Dissemination Level: Public ✓

ect has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

DELIVERABLE

Work Package	WP2 IT Infrastructure and Tools
Deliverable	D2.2 Architecture and Manual for Distributed Network Setup and Maintenance [M12, M24]
Task(s)	Task 2.2 Distributed Infrastructure Design and Development [M04-M18] Task 2.6 REFLOW OS Software Integration and Deployment [M06-M36]
Document Name	REFLOW OS
Due Date	M3: 30 November 2020
Submission Date	M3: 1 December 2020
Dissemination Level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> P – Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO – Confidential
Deliverable Lead	Dyne.org foundation (DYNE)
Author(s)	Ivan Minutillo, Mayel De Borniol, Denis Roio
Point of Contact	Andrea D'Intino; andrea@dyne.org
Reviewers	Vincent Bohlen (FOKUS), Andra Tanase and Andrei Martiniuc (ARIES)
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Plan <input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Working <input type="checkbox"/> Final <input type="checkbox"/> Approved
Abstract	This deliverable provides an introduction and a manual to the REFLOW OS, a system designed to operate federated nodes constituting the REFLOW network backend infrastructure. It is targeted for adoption by the Free and Open Source communities at large and consists of a living document that is publicly available online and maintained through the course of the REFLOW project.
Keywords	Circular Economy, Software, Valueflows, REA
Statement of Originality	This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Revision History

- 6 July 2020, Ivan Minutillo, DYNE, initial documentation setup
- 10 September 2020, Ivan Minutillo, DYNE, initial API documentation
- 20 September 2020, Ivan Minutillo, DYNE, material passport use-case
- 12 October 2020, Mayel de Borniol, DYNE, documentation of federated architecture
- 28 October 2020, Ivan Minutillo, DYNE, advanced API documentation
- 3 November 2020, Ivan Minutillo, DYNE, use-cases and glossary
- 6 November 2020, Denis Roio, DYNE, general revision and build and deploy docs
- 19 November 2020, Mayel de Borniol, DYNE, updated API documentation
- 20 November 2020, Ivan Minutillo, DYNE, detailed system requirements
- 27 November 2020, Denis Roio, DYNE, final revision

The information, documentation and figures in this deliverable are written by the REFLOW project consortium under EC grant agreement number 820937 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Table of Contents

Table of Contents

1. Living Document.....	5
2. Software.....	5

1. Living Document

This document is delivered in the format of a living document at the address REFLOWOS.dyne.org

The reason for this is that we adopt the free and open source methodology of research in delivering a process of development and documentation that is open to the appropriation and contribution by communities at large.

Our ambition is that of creating free and open source software that is adopted well beyond the pilot and use-cases contemplated in REFLOW and that survives the span of this project by facilitating the study, modification and redistribution of these outcomes where it may suit the needs of operating federated circular economy systems.

2. Software

Behind the documentation of REFLOWOS there is of course a software which has been developed ad-hoc for the project, drawing on the principles of the [Valueflows](#) ontology, the [Resource-Event-Agents](#) architecture, the Zenpub codebase and DECODE OS components providing means of privacy-by-design federation and authentication.

The development of the backend software during the span of the REFLOW project consisted of approximately of 2.500 code commits for a total of 40.000 lines of code, mostly in Erlang language using the Elixir framework, and 6.500 lines of comments.

A third-party technical analysis of the code-base is kindly provided by [Open Hub](#).

For any other information we invite the reader to refer to the [REFLOWOS](#) public documentation.

